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ECG Based Human Authentication using Wavelets and Random Forests

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ABSTRACT

The electrocardiogram (ECG) is an emerging novel biometric for human identification. It can be combined in a multi-modal biometric identification system or used alone for authentication of subjects. Its primary application can be in health care systems where the ECG is used for health measurements. It does furthermore, better than any other biometrics measures, deliver the proof of subject's being alive as extra information which other biometrics cannot deliver as easily. The main purpose of this study is to present a novel personal authentication approach for human authentication based on their ECG signals. We present a methodology for identity verification that quantifies the minimum number of heartbeats required to authenticate an enrolled individual. The cardiac signals were used to identify a total of 80 individuals obtained from four ECG databases from the Physionet database (MIT-BIH, ST-T, NSR, PTB) and an ECG database collected from 20 student volunteers from Paris Est University. Feature extraction was performed by using Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT). Wavelets have proved particularly effective for extracting discriminative features in ECG signal classification. The Random Forest was then presented for the ECG signals authentication. Preliminary experimental results indicate that the system is accurate and can achieve a low false negative rate, low false positive rate and a 100% subject recognition rate for healthy subjects with the reduced set of features.

KEYWORDS

ECG; human authentication; wavelet decomposition; random forests.

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Image Encryption Using Fibonacci-Lucas Transformation

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ABSTRACT

Secret communication techniques are of great demand since last 3000 years due to the need of information security and confidentiality at various levels of communication such as while communicating confidential personal data, patients' medical data, countries' defence and intelligence information, data related to examinations etc. With advancements in image processing research, Image encryption and Steganographic techniques have gained popularity over other forms of hidden communication techniques during the last few decades and a number of image encryption models are suggested by various researchers from time to time. In this paper, we are suggesting a new image encryption model based on Fibonacci and Lucas series.

KEYWORDS

Digital Image, Fibonacci series, Lucas series, Image scrambling, Fibonacci-Lucas map

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Video Surveillance in the Cloud?

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ABSTRACT

A high-resolution video surveillance management system incurs huge amounts of storage and network bandwidth. The current infrastructure required to support a high-resolution video surveillance management system (VMS) is expensive and time consuming to plan, implement and maintain. With the recent advances in cloud technologies, opportunity for the utilization of virtualization and the opportunity for distributed computing techniques of cloud storage have been pursued on the basis to find out if the various cloud computing services that are available can support the current requirements to a highresolution video surveillance management system. The research concludes, after investigating and comparing various Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) cloud computing provides what is possible to architect a VMS using cloud technologies; however, it is more expensive and it will require additional reviews for legal implications, as well as emerging threats and countermeasures associated with using cloud technologies for a video surveillance management system.

KEYWORDS

Video Surveillance, Cloud-Computing, IP-Camera, SPI Model, Cloud storage, virtualization

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Chaos Based Mixed Key stream Generation for Voice Data Encryption

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a high dimensional chaotic systems based mixed key stream generator is proposed to secure the voice data. As the voice-based communication becomes extensively vital in the application areas of military, voice over IP, voice-conferencing, phone banking, news telecasting etc. It greatly demands to preserve sensitive voice signals from the unauthorized listening and illegal usage over shared/open networks. To address the need, the designed key stream generator is employed to work as a symmetric encryption technique to protect voice bit streams over insecure transmission channel. The generator utilizes the features of high dimensional chaos like Lorenz and Chen systems to generate highly unpredictable and random-like sequences. The encryption key stream is dynamically extracted from the pre-processed chaotic mixed sequences, which are then applied to encrypt the voice bit stream for integrity protection of voice data. The experimental analyses like auto-correlation, signal distribution, parameter-residual deviation, key space and key-sensitivity demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed technique.

KEYWORDS

High dimensional chaotic systems, security, mixed key stream, voice encryption.

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Information Hiding in CSS: A Secure Scheme Text-Steganography Using Public Key Cryptosystem

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ABSTRACT

In many recent years, the programming world has been introduced about a new programming language for designing websites, it is CSS that can be used together with HTML to develop a web interface. And now, these two programming languages as if inseparably from each other. As a client-side scripting, CSS is visible by all users as the original script, but it cannot be granted changed. Website is a tool of information disseminator throughout the world, this is certainly can be used to a secret communication by using CSS as a message hider. This paper proposed a new scheme using web tools like CSS for hiding informations. This is a secret communication mechanism using text steganography techniques that is embedded messages on CSS files and is further encrypted using RSA as a public key cryptographic algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Text Steganography, Cryptography, Cascading Style Sheet (CSS), RSA Algorithm, public key algorithm

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Avoiding Wormhole Attack in MANET using Statistical Analysis Approach

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ABSTRACT

MANET is a collection of mobile hosts with wireless network interfaces that form a temporary network without any fixed infrastructure or centralized administration. MANET is infrastructure-less, lack of centralized monitoring and dynamic changing network topology. MANET is highly vulnerable to attack due to open error prone shared wireless medium. In this paper, we proposed an algorithm for avoiding and preventing the wormhole attacks in MANET using statistical analysis approach. Simulation results shows that proposed algorithm provides better security and performance in the presence of wormhole attack than conventional AODV.

KEYWORDS

MANET, Wormhole attack, Wormhole detection technique, Wormhole Avoidance, Statistical analysis.

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A Hybrid Approach to Counter Application Layer DDOS Attacks

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ABSTRACT

Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks are a growing threat across Internet, disrupting access to Information and services. Now a days, these attacks are targeting the application layer. Attackers are employing techniques that are very difficult to detect and mitigate. This paper proposes a hybrid detection scheme based on the trust information and information theory based metrics. Initial filtering is based on the trust value scored by the client. Then the information based metric, entropy, is applied for final filtering of suspicious flow. Trust value for a client is assigned by the server based on the access pattern of the client and updated everytime when the client contacts the server. The request from the client always includes this trust value to identify itself to the server. The Web user browsing behaviour (HTTP request rate, page viewing time and sequence of the requested objects) of the client is captured from the system log during non-attack cases. Based on the observation, Entropy of requests per session is calculated and used for rate limiting the flow further. A scheduler is included to schedule the session based on the trust value of the user and the system workload.

KEYWORDS

DDoS, Application Layer, Trust value &Entropy

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Improved Caesar Cipher with Random Number Generation Technique and Multistage Encryption

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ABSTRACT

Secured Communication involves Encryption process at the sending end and Decryption process at the receiving end of the communication system. Many Ciphers have been developed to provide data security . The efficiency of the Ciphers that are being used depends mainly on their throughput and memory requirement. Using of large key spaces with huge number of rounds with multiple complex operations may provide security but at the same time affects speed of operation. Hence in this paper we have proposed a method to improve Caesar cipher with random number generation technique for key generation operations. The Caesar cipher has been expanded so as to include alphabets, numbers and symbols. The original Caesar cipher was restricted only for alphabets. The key used for Caesar Substitution has been derived using a key Matrix Trace value restricted to Modulo 94. The Matrix elements are generated using recursive random number generation equation, the output of which solely depends on the value of seed selected . In this paper, we made an effort to incorporate modern cipher properties to classical cipher. The second stage of encryption has been performed using columnar transposition with arbitrary random order column selection. Thus the proposed Scheme is a hybrid version of classical and modern cipher properties. The proposed method provides appreciable Security with high throughput and occupies minimum memory space. The Method is resistant against brute-force attack with 93! Combinations of keys, for Caesar encryption.

KEYWORDS:

Encryption, Decryption, Substitution, Cipher, Random Number, Recursive, Primitive root, Plaintext, Cipher text

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Cryptanalyzing of Message Digest Algorithms MD4 and MD5

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ABSTRACT

Hash functions are tools used in integrity of messages, digital signatures and digital time stamping. Message digest algorithms started with public key cryptography for authentication. Digest algorithms compute some hash functions, which are message digest values based on a simple set of primitive operations of 32-bit words. Among the digest algorithms MD4 and MD5 are most popular. Both these algorithms perform a set of bitwise logical operations. They generate 128-bit digest values from a given message. Time complexity of MD5 is more than MD4 and hence somewhat slower to execute. The message digest algorithms MD4, MD5 have been discussed in detail. A new method has been introduced for obtaining collisions for reduced number of rounds of MD4 and MD5 algorithms. The time complexity, performance and attacks of MD4 and MD5 algorithm have been computed using this method. The strength has been computed on change in message; the new method can prove its strength.

KEYWORDS

Data integrity, Authentication, Non-repudiation, Time complexity

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Penetration Testing in Agile Software Development Projects

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ABSTRACT

Agile development methods are commonly used to iteratively develop the information systems and they can easily handle ever-changing business requirements. Scrum is one of the most popular agile software development frameworks. The popularity is caused by the simplified process framework and its focus on teamwork. The objective of Scrum is to deliver working software and demonstrate it to the customer faster and more frequent during the software development project. However the security requirements for the developing information systems have often a low priority. This requirements prioritization issue results in the situations where the solution meets all the business requirements but it is vulnerable to potential security threats. The major benefit of the Scrum framework is the iterative development approach and the opportunity to automate penetration tests. Therefore the security vulnerabilities can be discovered and solved more often which will positively contribute to the overall information system protection against potential hackers. In this research paper the authors propose how the agile software development framework Scrum can be enriched by considering the penetration tests and related security requirements during the software development lifecycle. Authors apply in this paper the knowledge and expertise from their previous work focused on development of the new information system penetration tests methodology PETA with focus on using COBIT 4.1 as the framework for management of these tests, and on previous work focused on tailoring the project management framework PRINCE2 with Scrum. The outcomes of this paper can be used primarily by the security managers, users, developers and auditors. The security managers may benefit from the iterative software development approach and penetration tests automation. The developers and users will better understand the importance of the penetration tests and they will learn how to effectively embed the tests into the agile development lifecycle. Last but not least the auditors may use the outcomes of this paper as recommendations for companies struggling with penetrations testing embedded in the agile software development process.

KEYWORDS

Agile Development, Penetration, Test, Scrum, Project Management, Software

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